

DABEER SI/FU/62**‘NO WORDS, JUST LINES’: SILENCE, FRAGMENTATION AND THE REFUSAL OF TESTIMONY IN *LITTLE SCRATCH*****ADIL HUSSAIN**Research Scholar, Department of English
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University of Kashmir, (J&K), India**Abstract**

This paper examines Rebecca Watson’s *Little Scratch* for narrative silence produced by a fractured temporality that leads to cognitive interruption. The novel details a single day in the life of the unnamed protagonist whose traumatic experiences and encounters are given to the reader obliquely, with a structure that divides the page into columns, completely renouncing traditional stylistic features of a linear narrative to account for the aborted thoughts and discontinuities. Through the novel’s choice of a style that renders the text as words spread across the page haphazardly, linked only tentatively through the narrative voice, such incoherence is foregrounded. Therefore, the voice does not fail to enunciate; it is rather the overstimulation which leads to exhaustion and fragmentation that becomes the operator of silence within the narrative. The paper draws on postclassical narratology and feminist theories of trauma in order to appreciate how the novel’s reconfiguration of silence acts as a structural principle of consciousness. When the novel’s typographical layout is read against its refusal to surrender to the demands of retrospective clarity by indulging in abrupt shifts in duration, the “micro-silences” produced can be seen as stalling memory as sensation overrides articulation, resulting in the collapse of narrative into staccato presence. The novel denies any eventual disclosure and the silences accentuate the ethical limits of testimony within everyday life. By positioning the novel within the discourse of culturally-mediated accelerated labour and attention, the paper highlights silence as a response to constant endeavour (and failure) of meaning-making in a world whose persistent demand for legibility leaves no space for the individual to respond in a meaningful form of narrative agency. *Little Scratch* emerges as a literary response that studies trauma without catharsis or a climactic appeal to deus ex machina for narrative repair. In this way, the dominant expectations of confession and resilience are made subservient to instability of experience and incoherence of the evocation of its memory, contributing to the debate on the poetics of absence and the ethics of the unsaid. Silence, therefore, is read not a form of lack in need of fulfilment but a condition that must be read on its own terms.

Keywords: Narrative Silence, Absence and Erasure, Postclassical Narratology, Trauma and the Unsaid, Feminist Narrative Ethics, Temporal Fragmentation

Introduction

Contemporary literature deals with trauma without a recourse to teleological narratives of recovery by mirroring the jeopardy of such experience. This ontological instability gives the text a texture that goes beyond modernist fragmentation. Published in 2021, Rebecca Watson's debut novel *Little Scratch* epitomises this movement through its radical overhaul of typographical structure that goes against the grain of conventional medium of print (and even electronic medium) along with its conventions of temporality. This is not a gimmick or trickery; such problematisation of representation and narrativization is, as will be seen, the only way the unnamed protagonist's experience of the aftermath of sexual violence can be communicated at interpersonal and intrapersonal levels. The novel relates events over a single Friday that cut across each other: the protagonist is a newsroom assistant who indulges in her mundane routine of corporate labour while her already-punctured present is assaulted by intrusive memory of her rape by her employer, giving it an air of digitally-mediated postmodern stream-of-consciousness narrative. The novel resists a climactic resolution or catharsis and instead through narrative silence that her fractured temporality produces in conjunction with the cognitive interruption in the form of elliptical thoughts and aborted ideas, it foregrounds the leftover of the subjectivity that remains post trauma. This paper examines how the novel reconfigures silence so that it governs the architectonics of the narrative by drawing on postclassical narratology and feminist trauma theory, particularly Monika Fludernik's concept of experientiality, Cvetkovich's archive of feelings, and Berlant's notion of lateral agency. Caruth's trauma theory and Luckhurst's critique of narrative act as a background whereby the paper examines the subject's silencing, showing the "inescapability of [trauma's] belated impact" (Caruth 7).

By renouncing linear clarity and opting for staccato presence, the novel at once draws attention to trauma residing in corporate labour and an attention economy governed by digital technologies that mediate such trauma (Watson "The Internet Has Split"). The resultant silence is not a lack of enunciation but a response that, with the help of the internet (especially social media), demonstrates how the failure of meaning-making reproduces itself even at the level of one's subjective consciousness. The self is multiplied across media and in its each iteration goes through the trauma with a different flavour, leading to a loss of legibility. As Watson points out:

There was the self before she was raped, the self during, the self after. But there was also the self when she was a child; a self when she was a teenager; a self when she was hungry or turned on; and within these selves, of course, were other selves.... These many selves manifested in [the protagonist's] surfacing memories, in the way she spoke to different people. It was in the page that split up and diverted. Technology added to the murmur. It presented a different her. It wasn't just about receiving a text but waiting for one; it was about where the internet could lead her. It allowed her to speak whilst saying nothing. The day was a crutch for my protagonist—it kept her together. The internet was part of that. (Watson "The Internet Has Split")

The Architecture of Fragmentation

The novel does not establish the backstory of the protagonist's trauma in a retrospective fashion but immerses the reader inside a moment of sensory cognition. This is driven home through the fragmented imagery and the narrative structure that continually postpones closure by actively undermining the grammar of fiction. Fludernik's concept of experientiality shifts narratology away from plot-based definitions of narrative toward the representation of human consciousness and embodied experience. To Martin Löschnigg, "the narrative rendering of individual experience and of a sense of identity is inextricably linked with basic structural patterns" (256–257). Löschnigg further expands upon Fludernik's concept of "experientiality" which, he asserts, becomes "basic to Fludernik's understanding of narrative" (259). Accordingly, the focus on "the presence of a 'human (anthropomorphic) experiencer' [is] an indispensable precondition of experientiality" (259). This is what generates the idea of self-identity as different elements of the narrative in an autobiography are put together. Löschnigg further explains the connection:

"Narrativized" understandings of identity focus on lived experience rather than on some quality which essentially "defines" a person, and on the capacity of narrative to impose order and coherence on what is otherwise a jumble of disconnected fragments of experiences and memories. The assumption that our experience and memories are organized in the form of narratives, however, is common to all the theorists mentioned, and is inseparably linked in their thinking with the heuristic function of narrative when it comes to creating a sense of identity. Peter Brooks, referring to Rousseau's *The Confessions*, keeps insisting that narrative provides the only means by which the autobiographer has access to his/her identity... (261–262)

While this gives the protagonist the opportunity to order their experientiality so as to get a "grasp identity as the telos of a coherent story" (262), the story's structure takes on the texture of the experience itself. This is evident in *Little Scratch*'s (almost) complete abandonment of a traditional plot trajectory in order to represent the immediate phenomenology of consciousness. The novel opens with the unnamed protagonist attempting to put her experience in traditional narrative fashion: "I am travelling through, passing my own capillaries, red lines rushing by, more red, caverns in my periphery like hulled strawberries, feeling a pain across my body (which I am in, am travelling through), tingling then sharp, sawlike, moving across me, rhythmic, back and forth, raking as I travel, beginning to emit a melodic sound" (Watson *Little Scratch* 1). However, as the narrative tries to accommodate the bodily concerns evoked by an off-stage traumatic experience, the narrative breaks down and is incapable of holding the experientiality in a "coherent" narrative form. This can be seen in the second half of the above-quoted sentence: "sounding / singing? is my body singing? is it in my veins? / (raking) rising / the sound is growing louder (raking) rising / as I continue travelling, reddening, (raking) rising" (1). The protagonist, thus, establishes a narrative space that internalises focalisation as the narrative becomes concave and rejects the traditional dealing with external environment. She attempts to register her physical

sensation without reducing it to the objective terminology of medicine, and in doing so, upsets the syntactical continuity of the novel. By introducing the rhythmic fragmentation and foregrounding it in the text, the novel establishes the body as a narrative environment. She points to her out-of-body experience wherein she views herself as a third person observer:

[C]rawling back through red to this —his face crawling looming back to sleep (inside my head) can see my own face too, even though I'm in my own body, inside my head, so I don't know why I'd be able to see my own face and yet, can see clearly, it wincing, and my stiff limbs, body completely still, no, stiff, still sounds too calm, it wasn't calm, can't have looked it, no, and there's my mouth, no no I know, I know how this plays out not now no... (2)

Watson repeatedly fractures the syntax when it comes to handling the traumatic experience as the sensation approaches articulation, producing micro-failures of narration each time so that trauma is seen exposing the inability of being given a directional order. Experience, rather than plot, is the organising principle of the narrative. With the bandwidth of typographical and narrative experimentation evoking micro-silences, the novel can be understood in terms of what Alison Gibbons sees as “multimodal novels” (1). While Gibbons does see inclusion of illustrations and images as a given for such novels, she outlines “varied typography” as one of the distinguishing features: “Such novels are highly sophisticated art forms, both in terms of their self-consciousness (using metafictional and intertextual reference, foregrounding materiality, innovative typographical textual layouts) and the invitations and demands they issue to readers” (2). Quoting Van Leeuwen, Gibbons asserts that “[t]ypographic communication is *multimodal*” (21). As such, for the desired effect to emerge in such texts, “narrative content, type-face, type-setting, graphic design, and images all have a role to play” (2). *Little Scratch* foregrounds the traumatic experience through its experimentation with typography, spatial arrangement and syntax. The following figure illustrates a page from the text, exemplifying the novel's experimental nature.

Fig. 1. Page from Rebecca Watson's *Little Scratch* illustrating the novel's typographical fragmentation, columnar layout and irregular spacing, which distribute the narrator's thoughts across the page. Reproduced from Watson, *Little Scratch* (McClelland & Stewart, 2020) (p. 13).

As the novel moves closer to traumatic exposure of the protagonist, the typographical architecture is dominated by parallel columns and competing textual streams. Opting for a bifurcated (and even trifurcated) tabulation of her experience, the narrative does not function merely as a monomodal sequential monologue but as a textual map of distributed consciousness that gives multiple mental process simultaneously. This is evident in how the narrator typographically presents to the reader the wallpaper “poster with an autoshaped smiley face”:

“there’s a face on it, the poster,
made of a colon : rotated . .

and a bracket () rotated (Watson Little Scratch 61)

The reader must keep track of events as they take place in the multilayered narrative as the layout reproduces what can be read as a kind of cognitive shuttlecock, with the simultaneous oscillation of attention between several registers such as mundane workplace tasks, ever-silenced bodily sensations, trauma-inducing intrusive memory and the escapist tendency of trivial observational detail. As these thematic concerns are reproduced through the columnarisation of the narrative, the printed page functions as a spatial representation of consciousness. The mundane storylines intermingle with the lingering memory of the itch to give it the embossed texture: “been ugh grabbing phone / snoozing! oh god 07:40 / must! get! up! (skin burning) / blood under my nails from fucking scratching in my sleep” (3). The protagonist’s description of her morning ritual consists of “clock-watching and [checking] WhatsApp notifications” (“Little Scratch”), monitoring her devices and performing repetitive tasks while the body is denied a proper exposition. This is one of the ways the novel asserts how its narrative environment revolves around attention economy. These micro-actions are later forked into separate textual columns as they progress in their own space, showing how the protagonist’s attention constantly moves between tasks. The repeated foregrounding of trivial acts of attention and juxtaposition of unrelated concerns (*q.v. p. 15*) signal that consciousness is structured less by narrative events than by the continual management of minor stimuli. As Alex Clark points out, “The story was a glimpse into the two different systems of being that most people experience simultaneously most of the time: the scheduled, material, almost mechanical flow of time (here, a lunch break, a conversation, minutes spent at a desk); and the private, interior anarchy of emotion, sensation and semi-articulation that unfolds in each moment.”

As the intrusive memories threaten to surface, the language is broken into isolated lexical fragments which, against the previous strategy of simultaneous tabulation of attention through columns, leads to the collapse of syntax into short phrases, interrupted clauses and single-word units scattered across the page. Rather than adopting a retrospective narrative of trauma, Watson’s structural approach mimics the manner in which traumatic cognition manifests as fragmentary sensory traces that resist narrative integration. Consequently, the page serves as a site where language approaches articulation yet consistently fails to stabilise into a coherent narrative. Watson frequently replaces syntactically complete sentences with clusters of sensory descriptors, acting as a strategy that replicates the pre-linguistic

immediacy of somatic experience before it can be organised into narrative memory:

I could just shout right now pedalling pedalling
 I was raped I was raped pedalling pedalling
 I was raped I was raped him turning, smiling
 I have the words but my mouth is closed smiling back smiling
 quiet and shut and I think it over and over I can't believe I'm smiling
 willing it to rise, force itself out of my mouth pedalling and smiling
 I was raped I was raped I was raped I was and saying nothing nothing
 raped I WAS RAPED RAPED BABE fucking nothing
 I WAS RAPED his arm extending left, me
 nothing is happening braking, pausing... (Watson *Little Scratch* 189)

As Heloise Wood asserts:

The form freewheels across the page as largely disordered and unpunctuated fragments of text recording all the banal and profound reflections of a day. Life's constant barrage of interruptions – catcalls, toilet-door posters, WhatsApp messages, dialogue and overheard conversations – are detailed minutely and seamlessly alongside the protagonist's own thoughts. While sometimes confusing – how best to read this anarchic word jungle? – it also transports us with immediacy into her disordered state of mind. Simultaneously, she attempts to repress the violence she has suffered, to accept lowly isolation in an open-plan office while nursing her own writing ambitions and to support her boyfriend (“my him”) without appearing clingy.

Absence works as a generative narrative strategy where what is left unsaid or erased carries more weight than what is articulated. Absence, therefore, is handled by Watson's typographical fragmentation which, as Gibbons observes, operates as a semiotic system, capable of expressing cognitive states that exceed the capacity of conventional syntax. This refusal of representational fullness is an ethical gesture that resists the spectacle of trauma and acknowledges the limits of what can be rendered. It must be noted that Watson does not rely primarily on syntax but rather on the spatial organisation of the page itself. The gaps between different experiential spheres at once demonstrate how such experiences fragment the consciousness of the protagonist while refusing to surrender to the overall structure of the narrative that calls for a conventional model of tragedy (such as Freytag's) that resolves cathartically. The reader must therefore traverse the page non-linearly, navigating between textual islands. In this sense, the novel's typographical design functions as a diagram of consciousness, mapping the protagonist's cognitive state across the material surface of the book. This is further complicated by the intrusion of digital communication technologies: at one point, the novel formalises the ever present logic of the Twitter feed (Watson *Little Scratch* 143) as the protagonist engaging with *her* social media feed” (153), sees “money falling, readers falling, me falling down the feed” (140) in a manner of dissolution. Speaking strictly in terms of those instances, *Little Scratch* can be read as a postdigital social media novel that captures the relentless data-saturation of contemporary consciousness. As Clark suggests: “in the modern world, where

communication is truncated even when we have too much to say; and in the modern novel, where a character must find a way to name her own experience, even if only to herself." Anna Aslanyan further clarifies the novel's dealing with social media: "The novel's non-linear structure evokes a tendency to toggle between things that no longer seems particularly neurotic in the digital era.... From all-consuming social media posts, messages and blogs, it is only a small step to autofiction, a genre often confused with therapy." In this way, *Little Scratch*, which is "as addictive as web browsing" (Aslanyan), and deals with, as Nell Stevens asserts, the "intermittent hum of electronic communications," which constitutes one of its three "simultaneous realities" ("Little Scratch"), can be read as a social media novel.

The Ethics of the Unsaid

The novel's juxtaposition of the mundane with the protagonist's attempts to give voice to her traumatic experience which end in mere imagined disclosures can best be understood in Ann Cvetkovich's concept of the "archive of feelings." The narrative often returns to stage testimony and confession as mental rehearsal that, true to the nature of the novel, never "find[s] words to unveil," (Watson *Little Scratch* 201) the right words for interpersonal expression:

[H]ad to form, have to form, tomorrow I will form the beginning tomorrow I will begin will open up (open up as in confess yes but also open up a mental wound, pick the scab all of that tomorrow) maybe tomorrow too I will stop picking my own actual scabs, maybe that too tomorrow, no more scratching, none of that, no no no tomorrow, tomorrow, words new, nails tucked away, tomorrow, ignoring the cliché of tomorrow (if tomorrow is true, then why not do it now? wake your snuffling darling and do it now?) no, he's asleep, me drowsing too, but I will form soon I will form, I'm okay now and tomorrow I will form and be okay, further okay... (201)

At the close of the novel, the protagonist's confession of her need for support and counselling also ends in another postponement as she evokes a simultaneous impulse of concealment: "I'm okay really really I need to speak / need to tell but for the moment I'm okay really / eyes closing telling myself that again I'm okay I'm okay I'm okay / I'm okay I'm okay I'm okay okay okay remember that / soon I might need to... eyes dissolving / subsiding / returning / lines of red" (201–202). The repetition that cuts across her mental compartments emphasises the level of effort required for the suppression. Rather than speaking up about the trauma, she can only evoke the psychological labour of suppressing it. The protagonist's repeated insistence that she is "okay" replaces narrative disclosure with self-regulation, showing how silence becomes a strategy for sustaining the appearance of normality. The unspoken trauma has the bodily symptom of scratching, which becomes the physical manifestation of psychological disturbance, as the only means through which it maintains its presence. This means that the harsh repetition of daily rituals (whether at the workplace or back home) becomes her only means (apart from what Luckhurst calls "narrative anachrony as a symptom of buried trauma" (Luckhurst 105)) to assert the presence of trauma which

otherwise threatens to slide her into a mental state as evident in her persistence scratching:

...this dreaded fucking desk? anything but that look at me now lost in linearity, where is the freedom in my head, to not have to only move side to side, stuck in straight lines every morning once I've arrived in this office, breaking myself in every morning, having to loosen the numbness punch by punch but yes I can feel my head loosening, freeing, it's always this way, numbness ebbs, visits, interrupts, but always pushed down eventually taking my head away, but always giving it back (or do I wrench it back? I am not sure but I am tired certainly, so I might have been wrenching), takes a while to unstick, colleague passing, who always makes tea for the assistant in the corner, who, I wonder, perhaps knows everything, it seems so, in her soft look, her incessant tea and the no questions, no questions, apart from tea, and sometimes... (Watson Little Scratch 52)

This means that while the narrative shifts the representation of trauma from speech to the body, the enumeration of repetitive tasks is her way of resistance to a total surrender to trauma. Felman and Laub describe testimony as an attempt to approach a truth that resists direct narration: "Since the testimony dwells on historicity as a relationship to death, and since the act of writing—the act of making the artistic statement of the novel—is itself presented as an act of bearing witness to the trauma of survival, the *event* to which the testimony points and which it attempts to comprehend and grasp is enigmatically, at once historical and clinical" (8). Watson's novel radicalises this idea by staging testimony as imagined disclosure rather than articulated speech. Traumatic experience, therefore, requires a particular mode of testimony which may not take the form of straightforward narration as it is tasked with revealing a deep-seated emotion that escapes standard language. Thus, Mallarmé's experimentation with language becomes "the very principle of poetic insight and the very core of the event of poetry which makes precisely language—through its breathless gasps—speak ahead of knowledge and awareness and break through the limits of its own conscious understanding" (21). Reading Watson's stylistic experimentation in terms of Cathy Caruth's "constitutive function of latency" (18) gives one the position to argue that the symptomatic repetition becomes the only way trauma becomes visible later, as it is not fully understood at the moment it occurs. To Caruth, the post-facto revival of trauma "through intrusive flashbacks, recurring dreams, or later situations that repeat or echo the original" (Luckhurst 1), becomes the primary site where trauma is actually experienced as "trauma is not locatable in the simple violent or original event in an individual's past" (Caruth 4):

The experience of trauma, the fact of latency, would thus seem to consist, not in the forgetting of a reality that can hence never be fully known, but in an inherent latency within the experience itself.¹¹ The historical power of the trauma is not just that the experience is repeated after its forgetting, but that it is only in and through its inherent forgetting that it is first experienced at all. (17)

This explains why traumatic events often cannot be narrated coherently when they first occur as trauma does not reside in the event itself. The latency refers to necessary distance from the actual event and its returns through repetition, memory and symptom takes a toll on the everyday life of the subject. Ann Cvetkovich argues that trauma may appear through ordinary emotional states rather than dramatic events. As Cvetkovich puts it, such events “haunt the present” as they [appear] in textures of everyday emotional life that don’t necessarily seem traumatic” (6). As such, the “nuances of everyday emotional life contain the residues that are left by traumatic histories, and they too belong in the archive of trauma” (280). Since “trauma disrupts memory, and therefore identity” (Luckhurst 1), Watson situates the protagonist’s trauma within mundane routines rather than explicit testimony to relate its effect in a language that does not compromise with its texture. This applies to the “narrative anachrony” in *Little Scratch*, whereby the narrative present is constantly punctured by the past, creating a feeling of *Nachträglichkeit*, or belatedness, where markers of trauma are encountered before their significance can be fully comprehended. The protagonist’s waking thoughts, for instance, are a site of struggle between the present need to get up for work and the looming face of her boss inside her head. This is what Watson sees as her “stream of experience” with her use of the “honest present tense” (as a review puts it). Thanks to the novel’s system of interweaving columns and parallel channels which allows for the representation of these simultaneities, the protagonist’s physical sensations and discursive thoughts battle in a saturated now.

Lateral Agency and the Refusal of Repair

The implications are not only personal for the subject but, as Cvetkovich posits, “trauma forges overt connections between politics and emotion” (3). Accordingly, *Little Scratch* does not present a romanticised version of recovery from trauma but refuses the therapeutic narrative of recovery, instead portraying survival as a series of lateral adjustments within an environment structured by continuous labour and exhausted attention. A conventional recovery narrative would rely on what Berlant sees as the traumatised subject making use of “conventional good-life fantasies—say, of enduring reciprocity in couples, families, political systems, institutions, markets, and at work” to escape their reality which is full of “instability, fragility” (2). The tussle between the lingering trauma and everyday mundanity leads to an “impasse”. Berlant definition of impasse aptly sums up Watson’s narrative strategy as it remains confined to a single day that never progresses toward resolution:

“[T]he impasse is a stretch of time in which one moves around with a sense that the world is at once intensely present and enigmatic, such that the activity of living demands both a wandering absorptive awareness and a hypervigilance that collects material that might help to clarify things, maintain one’s sea legs, and coordinate the standard melodramatic crises with those processes that have not yet found their genre of event. (4)

While this gives the protagonist means of survival as she is, to use Berlant’s words, “figuring out how to stay attached to life from within it, and to protect what optimism they have for that, at least” (10), the capitalist system of continual attention and constant consumption prevents any meaningful disruption of the

impasse. Berlant conceptualises this mode of survival as a form of *lateral agency* in which subjects remain within conditions of crisis but develop minor strategies for endurance. Rather than producing transformation, such agency consists of small adjustments that allow subjects to continue living within compromised environments. As Jonathan Crary puts it, contemporary capitalism produces a form of “inscription of human life into duration without breaks, defined by a principle of continuous functioning” (8). This “24/7 environment has the semblance of a social world” but is sterile and regulated by “machinic performance and a suspension of living” (9). The protagonist of *Little Scratch* frames everyday life as a repetitive sequence of obligations that suggests fatigue with routine as well as acceptance of its inevitability: “got to do this thing again, the waking up thing, the day thing, the work thing, the disentangling from my duvet thing, this is something, this is a thing I have to do then” (Watson *Little Scratch* 3). The setting of *Little Scratch* in a high-pressure London newsroom is central to its exploration of overstimulation as a site of cognitive fragmentation. The protagonist’s day is defined by the scheduled, material flow of time, punctuated by the mechanical tasks of office administration. In such an environment, even the most minimal act of taking care of one’s body as a way of staying “attached to life from within it” feels like an obligation and a set of computer instructions:

water (my *head* disagrees)
 pint glass by bed glugging
 ah, sweet water glugging
 toes out from under duvet now (3)

Nevertheless, such everyday bodily rituals provide temporary stability within the rhythm of the day. The fact that she is “swaying a little but catching self” (4) reflects her attempt to regulate her life. This is evident in the protagonist’s use of the word “enough” as a linguistic tool to suspend her intrusive thoughts and regain focus on the mundane, empirical reality (see for instance pp. 47, 65, 83, 103, 140). Her recurring self-admonitions such as “STOPPING SCRATCHING RIGHT NOW” (124) act as narrative refrain. As such, the subject remains functional through minor acts of correction rather than meaningful change. This is exemplified by her uses of physical movement as a somatic mantra to snap out of the intrusive memories: “napping head, moving off, out of bathroom, back down corridor, down down down to dreaded desk / leaning hand, elegantly poised over tea, fingers extending across the rim — spider-like” (47).

At the same time, the protagonist does not feel particularly attached to her body and suggests that “none of these [body parts] are mine” (4). The repeated scratching of her body transforms it into a register of stress, revealing how physical gestures replace narrative articulation. She gets access to her body only through physical hurt, giving her a mechanism to somehow deal with her trauma.

I have made that clear, reserved enough space in my head for acknowledging that I am not fine) but yes it is the point in the day where this morning no longer feels like this morning and yet it was obviously I didn't have time to dawdle, to float I just drank water and showered and hurried and felt okay because I did not have time to feel any other way, a

new tactic perhaps, setting my alarm late, overfilling my time (I know that this will not work, but I consider it, if only to fill the space where I could be thinking something else) yes from now on I'll arrive everywhere late, and start everything late, and oversubscribe until my eyes burst and my head hurts (it already does, but even more I guess) body stretched until I do not know who I am or what I want or where I am or how I got here or what happened to me that time... (121)

With the protagonist's efforts to suppress her trauma, the body records its persistence as it nullifies the success of such attempts. Through the representation of sexual violence, *Little Scratch* turns the personal tragedy into a political experience by resisting the climactic entry of deus ex machina who, in a traditional survivor story, introduces an emotional script often imposed on survivors. While Watson's protagonist attempts to repress the violence she has suffered by engaging in a form of narrative withholding that acknowledges the ethical limits of testimony within everyday life, such silence is not a passive failure to speak but an active narrative and ethical strategy. To Cvetkovich, trauma is frequently marked by forgetting and dissociation, putting pressure on conventional forms of documentation and representation. The novel responds to this pressure by creating an unusual archive of feelings, where the memory of trauma is embedded in the ephemeral material artifacts of a day, such as WhatsApp messages, toilet door posters and office emails. The protagonist's perpetual scratching of her skin, particularly in hidden places like behind her knees, serves as a primary signifier of her trauma. This act is described as a desire to purge herself, a physical manifestation of a memory that cannot be integrated. The scratching can be seen as a form of adjustment that allows her to live on in an impasse. As Berlant asserts, "In the impasse induced by crisis, being treads water; mainly, it does not drown" (10). In the scene where the protagonist pulls her tights down in a toilet cubicle, she instructs herself not to scratch, yet her body moves faster to get its pound of flesh before she can stop herself. The sensation of scratching becomes an operator of silence, stalling the narrator's ability to articulate her pain by replacing thought with raw physical feeling.

The protagonist seems to inflict harm to herself through a continual exhaustion at the workplace. To her, this acts as a way to keep herself in a quasi-comatose state when she gets back from work. The imperative of attaining a state of functionality each morning provides her life with a semblance of coherence:

I've arrived in this office, breaking myself in every morning, having to loosen the numbness punch by punch but yes I can feel my head loosening, freeing, it's always this way, numbness ebbs, visits, interrupts, but always pushed down eventually taking my head away, but always giving it back (or do I wrench it back? I am not sure but I am tired certainly, so I might have been wrenching), takes a while to unstick... (Watson *Little Scratch* 52)

Even the workplace is a constant reminder of her sexual abuse which constantly destroys her narrative reality. The "HARASSMENT IN THE WORKPLACE" (99) email makes her doubt her version of events as she starts to feel that she must have been "imagining it then, not feeling" (101). The clinical, corporate language

of the email acts as a violent intrusion into her psyche. The juxtaposition of her lived reality versus the sterile “policy” of the office creates a sense of cognitive dissonance. The constant barrage of interruptions, from corporate emails about sexual harassment to the itemisation of her boss’s receipts, creates a state of overstimulation that leads to cognitive exhaustion. The protagonist is forced to work at the very desk where she was raped, under the supervision of the same boss. The rhythmic cadence of the protagonist descending “down down down to dreaded desk” (46) evokes a Dantesque progression in which she can be seen as navigating various circles of a contemporary corporate inferno:

...down into the dreaded corridor, through dreaded swing doors, why past dreaded toilet, am kitchen on dreaded left, I dreaded desk dreaded desk here approaching (dread) desk belting myself in for the day (metaphorically) I wonder though belting myself what sort of job would involve literally... (38)

This environment creates a state of chronic hyperarousal and numbness, where the trauma is not a past event but a persistent feature of the ordinary. The novel’s focus on the minutiae of daily existence, such as drinking eight glasses of water or overthinking the use of heart emojis, demonstrates how trauma embeds itself at the level of the everyday. By refusing to provide a climactic scene of narrative repair, Watson contributes to the debate on the poetics of absence and the ethics of the unsaid. The protagonist’s silence towards her mother, her boyfriend, and her colleagues is a strategy of self-protection that allows her to keep her sense of self intact amidst a world that offers no meaningful form of narrative agency.

Conclusion

By giving the reader a snippet of the unnamed protagonist’s life, *Little Scratch* demonstrates how traditional trauma narratives that end with a climactic moment of disclosure or emotional clarity are rendered impossible by the attention economy of corporate reality. The text’s narrative strategy, typographical layout and constant shuttling of perspective which carries ambivalence towards the protagonist’s body aptly highlight the limits of articulation through the medium of the novel. What fills the (literal) gaps between the columnarised text is the structural principle of silence that does not represent absence. When read through the frameworks of Fludernik’s experientiality, Cvetkovich’s archive of feelings, and Berlant’s lateral agency, silence emerges as the organising principle of the novel’s fragmented typography, which reconfigures storytelling to such an extent that a conventional breakdown is nullified. Watson’s layout translates thought directly into a visual form through the split columns and lexical fragments that do more than just describe a mind; they recreate the jagged rhythms of the protagonist’s internal life. The reader meets thought in its rawest state as they are directly presented with the unfinished, the interrupted and the frequently drowned out by noise without polish or grammatical conjunction. The page becomes a diagram of a mind rather than a simple vehicle for a plot as Watson refuses to turn trauma into a tidy, coherent object. Interestingly, the fragments that we get to put together, never quite coalesce into a full account of what happened. The unsaid becomes its own archive, built from sensations rather than clear statements. By not reconstructing the traumatic event in detail, Watson refuses to make the

protagonist's suffering a spectacle. She preserves the opacity of the experience while pointing toward the social pressures that keep her silent. This refusal to speak is not just a psychological block; it is a recognition that speaking in a conventional way might just reinforce the systems that caused the harm. *Little Scratch* suggests that silence can be a form of resistance, an insistence that some things cannot (and should not) be turned into a neat story.

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